

IZOHLOVCHI KOMPONENTLARING SINTAKSEM TAHLILI

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Annotation *Izohlovchi komponentlarning sintaktik aloqalarini ingliz tili sodda gap tarkibidagi yunksion modellar yordamida aniqlash, komponentlarga va sintaksemalarga ajratish hamda ular ifodalagan sintaksemalarni ochib berishdan iborat. Mazkur maqolamizda biz asosiy urg'uni tobe komponentlar tahliliga qaratar ekanmiz, uch valentli tobe sintaktik birlikning ikkinchi darajali bo'lakka nisbatan izohlovchi bo'lib kelish holatlarini o'qqanib chiqamiz.*

Kalit so'zlar: *yunksion model, izohlovchi komponent, , sodda gap, strukturaviy tahlil, komponent model, subordinativ aloqa, uch valentlik tobe sintaktik birlik*

Gap tahlili nazariyasining turli masalalariga bag'ishlangan ko'pchilik tadqiqotlarida - muammo gap bo'laklariga savol berish xususiyatlaridan kelib chiqqan holda tadqiq etilgan. Zero, o'tgan asrning so'nggi choragida gap tahlilining bir qator yangicha usullari keltirilgan bo'lsa-da, hanuzgacha gap tahlili deganda ko'pchilik til o'rganuvchilar bosh bo'laklar va ikkinchi darajali bo'laklar asosida tahlil qilishni tushunadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan tilshunoslikda yechimini kutayotgan muammolardan biri, ya'ni ingliz tili gap qurilmalarining paradigmatic va sintagmatic yo'nalishlarida gap bo'laklarining semantikasini aniqlash, gaplarni sintaktik komponent tarkibi asosida tahlil qilish va sintaktik birliklarning semantikasini ochib berish kabi ustuvor yo'nalishlarda tadqiqotlar olib borilishi taqazo etiladi.

Izohlovchi tobe komponentlarning sintaksem tahlili

Izohlovchi gap qurilmasida noyadroviy appozitiv predikativ 1 komponentlari o'rnida kelganda tayanch komponentga bevosita appozitiv aloqa asosida bog'lanib,

gap tarkibida ikkinchi sintaktik aloqa, ya'ni bilvosita ikki marta predikativ aloqa asosida ishtirok etadi. Shu tufayli u uch valentli sintaktik birlik sanaladi. Ma'lumki, appozitiv aloqa bir komponentni boshqa komponent bilan bog'lab, shu orqali uchinchi sintaktik birlik bilan bilvosita aloqaga kirishadi. Shu bois V.A.Severyanovanning fikriga ko'ra, bir tomondan o'sha komponentning differensial sintaktik belgisi appozitivlikni anglatadi, ikkinchi tomondan, ya'ni bilvosita bog'lanish natijasida yadro predikativ 1, yadro predikativ 2, noyadroviy tobe komponentlardan birini ifodalaydi [6, 293]. Mazkur maqolamizda biz asosiy urg'uni tobe komponentlar tahliliga qaratar ekanmiz, uch valentli tobe sintaktik birlikning ikkinchi darajali bo'lakka nisbatan izohlovchi bo'lib kelish holatlarini o'rganib chiqamiz.

Noyadroviy appozitiv tobe (NAD) komponenti o'rnida kelgan sintaktik birliklarning sintaksem tahlili. Noyadroviy appozitiv tobe komponent o'rnida kelgan sintaktik birlik gap qurilmasida eksplitsit tarzda, ya'ni bevosita appozitiv aloqa asosida bog'lanadi. Uning implitsit tarzda yoki bilvosita bog'lanishi yadro predikativ va subordinativ aloqalar asosida namoyon bo'ladi.

Quyidagi gaplar sintaksemalarga ajratib tahlil qilinganda uch valentli noyadroviy appozitiv tobe komponentlar kategorial belgilardan substansiallik bazasida yadro predikativ aloqa asosida nokategorial belgilardan identifikatsiyalovchi sintaksemi, subordinativ aloqa asosida obyekt, sotsiativ (hamkorlik), agentiv, atributsion sintaksemalarni ifodalashi ayon bo'ladi:

1. *They lifted down Zila, his wife (GSTU, 181).*

2. *He had left a young widow, Mary (RGH, 12).*

Ushbu ikkala sodda gapda uch valentli noyadroviy appozitiv tobe komponentlar *his wife* (1) sintaktik birlik *Zila* bilan, *Mary* (2) esa *a young widow* bilan bevosita appozitiv aloqa asosida bog'langani tufayli ular substansial identifikatsiyalovchi sintaksemalarni ifodalaydi. Bu ifodani transformatsiya metodining quyidagi usuli orqali tasvirlash mumkin:

(1) *They lifted down Zila, his wife* → *Zila is his wife.*

(2) *He had left a young widow, Mary* → *A young widow is Mary.*

Ushbu izohlovchi sintaktik birliklar yadro predikativ 2 oʻrnida kelgan *lifted down* (1) va *had left* (2) komponentlar bilan bilvosita subordinativ aloqa asosida bogʻlanib, obyekt sintaksemani namoyon qiladi. Bu sintaksemaning ifodalanishini tushirib qoldirish hamda transformatsiya passivizatsiya usullari orqali koʻrsatish mumkin:

(1) *They lifted down Zila, his wife* → *they lifted down ... his wife* → *his wife was lifted down by them.*

(2) *He had left a young widow, Mary* → *he had left ... Mary* → *Mary had been left by him.*

Transformatsiya passivizatsiyadan koʻrinadiki, noyadroviy appozitiv tobe komponent yadro predikativ 1 komponenti oʻrnida kelib, yadro predikativ aloqa asosida bilvosita ishtirok etishi *his wife* (1), *Mary* (2) elementlarining uch valentli sintaktik birliklar ekanligidan dalolat beradi. Demak, noyadroviy appozitiv tobe komponentlar *his wife* va *Mary* substansial identifikatsiyalovchi obyekt sintaksemani ifodalaydi. Shuningdek, noyadroviy appozitiv tobe sintaktik birliklar substansial identifikatsiyalovchi obyekt agentiv sintaksemani ham ifodalashi mumkin .

Tobe sintaktik birliklar gap qurilmasida NAD komponent oʻrnida kelganda identifikatsiyalovchi sintaksemadan tashqari sotsiativ (hamkorlik) sintaksemani ham ifodalashi mumkin:

... he had run off with that foreign girl – a governess (GSTU, 38).

Tobe sintaktik birlik appozitiv aloqa asosida identifikatsiyalovchi sintaksemani ifodalaydi:

he had run off with that foreign girl – a governess → *... girl is a governess.*

Sotsiativlikning ifodalanishini transformatsiya metodning qoʻshimcha qilish vatushirib qoldirish usullari orqali isbotlash mumkin :

(4)...*he had run off with that foreign girl – a governess* → *he had run off with ... a governess* → *he had run off together with a governess* yoki *he had run off with a governess* → *he and a governess had run off.*

Yuqorida keltirilgan gaplar tahlilining ko‘rsatishicha, qayd etilgan sintaksemalardan tashqari tobe sintaktik birliklar noyadroviy appozitiv tobe komponent o‘rnida kelganda atributsion (predmet yoki shaxsni anglatib, shu predmet yoki shaxs tufayli ish-harakatning bajarilishidir) hamda tasniflovchi (klassifitsiruyushiy) sintaksemalarni ifodalashi mumkin:

He made his report to Mr. Greeley, his own tructure chief (SM, 145).

Berilgan ushbu gapda tobe *chief* NAD komponenti o‘rnida kelgan sintaktik birlikning identifikatsiyalovchi atributsion sintaksemalarni ifodalashini transformatsiya metodining almashtirish, savol qo‘yish, tushirib qoldirish usullaridan foydalanib izohlash mumkin:

a) identifikatsiyalovchi sintaksema;

(5) *He made his report to Mr. Greeley, his own particular chief* → ... *Mr. Greeley, his own particular chief* → *Mr. Greeley was his own particular chief.*

b) atributsion sintaksema:

(5) *He made his report to Mr. Greeley, his own particular chief* → *He made his report to ... his own particular chief* → *To whom did he make his report?* Yoki *For the sake of whom did he make his report?*

Yuqorida tahlil qilingan misollardan ma’lumki, uch valentli noyadroviy appozitiv tobe komponentlar gap qurilmasida turli xil differensial sintaktik-semantik belgilarni ifodalashi hamda bir, ikki, uch valentli bo‘lishi ham mumkin. Uch valentli noyadroviy tobe komponent ifodalagan sintaksemalarning sintaktik aloqalar asosida boshqa sintaksemalar bilan bog‘lanish qonuniyatlariga e’tibor beradigan bo‘lsak, appozitiv aloqa asosida aniqlangan barcha identifikatsiyalovchi sintaksemalar faqat identifikatsiyalanuvchi sintaksema bilan bog‘lanadi. Xulosa qilib

umumlashtiradigan bo‘lsak, uch valentli noyadroviy appozitiv tobe komponent to‘rt xil sintaksemani o‘zida mujassamlantira oladi.

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